

An extraordinary 2021 *Heterosigma akashiwo* (Raphidophyte) bloom in Chile: large-scale farmed salmon mortality associated with unusual environmental conditions

Marco Pinto-Torres^{1,2,3*}, Maximiliano J. Vergara-Jara¹, Javier Paredes-Mella¹, Ana Flores-Leñero¹, Osvaldo Artal⁴, Elías Pinilla⁴, Andrea Corredor², Jorge I. Mardones^{1,2*}

¹ Centro de Estudios de Algas Nocivas (CREAN), Instituto de Fomento Pesquero (IFOP), Puerto Montt, Chile; ² Centro de Investigación en Dinámica de Ecosistemas Marinos de Altas Latitudes (IDEAL), Valdivia, Chile; ³ Escuela de Graduados Programa de Doctorado en Ciencias de la Acuicultura, Universidad Austral de Chile, Puerto Montt, Chile; ⁴ Centro Tecnológico Para la Acuicultura (CTPA)-Putemún, Instituto de Fomento Pesquero (IFOP), Castro, Chile.

*corresponding author's email: marcoapintot@gmail.com, jorge.mardones@ifop.cl

Abstract

During early Austral Autumn, the Comau fjord (42° S) experienced an extraordinary HAB event that led to losses of more than 6,000 tons of farmed salmon during an extremely low rain – high solar radiation period. Field sampling and monitoring activities were carried out at the bloom site in the vicinity of farming cages close to the Lloncochaigua river mouth (Los Lagos Region). CTD data from the fjord transect, where some of the highest mortalities occurred, showed a pronounced stratification with high chlorophyll (70 mg L⁻¹), low salinity (~ 24), high temperature (~17 °C), high dissolved oxygen values at the surface (> 10 mg L⁻¹), and a shallow pycnocline (mostly in the upper 10 m of the water column). At the surface, cell abundances of *H. akashiwo* reached to ~70,000 cells mL⁻¹ and significantly lower abundances along with increasing depth. Hydrodynamic modeled particulate dispersion (Party - MOSA) showed high retention times in the Comau fjord, suggesting that this physical driver might have an important role in enhancing cell aggregation processes (patchiness) at the very surface layer of the water column. Finally, the end of the bloom was associated with cloudy - rainy weather. These observations highlight the need for differentiated strategies to tackle fast developing HAB events in Chilean Patagonia.

Keywords: Raphidophyte, cell abundances, water column, fish mortality, Chilean Patagonia

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Introduction

The Raphidophyte *Heterosigma akashiwo* is a small (from 10 to 20 μm in length) golden-brown phytoflagellate, which has been implicated in massive fish kill events worldwide. *Heterosigma akashiwo* can be considered as an eurythermic and euryhaline species, due to its distribution in different coastal ecosystems such as estuaries and bays where it colonizes effectively due to the rapid rates of cell division (up to five or six per day), which are associated with the characteristics of the water column, that allow its rapid cell growth (Smayda, 2007). This is due to the plasticity it presents to changes in salinity (between 5 and 35) and temperature (from 12° to 21 °C) (Martínez *et al.*, 2010). Associated with its high colonizing capacity in highly stratified systems, which turns seawater into an oxidized brown color (Honjo, 1993).

Blooms can be transient or remain for months if water column stratification persists (Taylor *et al.*, 1994). Even in nearby locations within the same general area, some blooms may be highly lethal as described in China, Japan, New Zealand, Canada and the United States (Kempton *et al.*, 2008; Rensel *et al.*, 2010), while others are relatively benign. Physical or biological conditions that affect toxicity have not been identified and may differ considerably from those conducive to bloom formation.

The toxicological mechanisms responsible for the ichthyotoxic properties of *H. akashiwo* are currently under debate. For raphidophytes, three main mechanisms have been proposed: i) production of neurotoxins (*e.g.* brevetoxins), ii) high content of free fatty acids, and iii) production of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

ROS generated during harmful algal blooms have been linked to lesions of gill tissue in fish, including epithelial uplift, cell necrosis, and disruption of chloride cells. These wounds, in turn, produce massive mucus secretion from the gills and physiological responses such as hypoxia, suffocation, and subsequent death (Astuya *et al.*, 2018; Mardones *et al.*, 2021).

In the case of the southern fjord system of Chile (41° S), historical events of harmful algal blooms (HAB) have been reported affecting the salmon farming industry since 1982 to date. Fish mortality has often been associated with the rapid growth of HAB-forming species, but the harmful effect can also be associated with any species of phytoplankton that rapidly increases their biomass, which can have negative effects on the ecosystem. In this study, we report an extraordinary HAB event produced by *H. akashiwo* due to unusual environmental conditions during 2021 in southern Chile, generating more than 6,000 tons in salmon mortality (report salmon farming).

Material and Methods

An unusual HAB produced by *H. akashiwo* was recorded during March and April 2021 in the Comau fjord (42° S, Los Lagos region; Fig. 1). During this event, four sampling stations were selected in a transect defined from East to West and fluorescence, salinity, temperature and dissolved oxygen (DO) profiled using a SAIV A/S CTD-F/O model SD204. All stations were sampled for phytoplankton collection at discrete depths (0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 m) using a 2.5 L Niskin bottle. Cell counts were carried out immediately after sampling

using an inverted microscope. To estimate the water circulation within the fjord, the dispersion of particles was modeled using the Parti-MOSA platform every 6 h for 12 days (from March 25 to April 7) at a depth of 5 m, and with a dispersion radius of 250 m.

Results and Discussion

Heterosigma akashiwo was the dominant species in the Comau fjord during the outbreak (more than 90% of the phytoplankton assemblage). Most of the algal biomass was detected in the water surface producing dense cell aggregations (Fig. 2).

The cell concentrations quantified *in situ* reached a range over 70,000 cells mL⁻¹ (Fig. 3), which were maintained for weeks, independent of the weather characteristics (rain and wind).

Fig. 1. Map of Chile. Red circle showing the Comau Fjord in 42° S, Los Lagos region.

The hydrological characteristics of the water column showed a highly stratified two-layer system, with salinities between 25 to 29 for the surface layer and > 31 for the subsurface layer (below 10 m). The thermocline showed

variations with a range between 11 and 16 °C, from the surface to 30 m (Figs. 4A, B).

The maximum fluorescence was detected on the surface with a value of 75 ug L⁻¹, decreasing steadily up to 4 m (Fig. 4C) corresponding with maximum cell abundances and the structure of the pycnocline. The DO measurements showed a maximum of 10 mg L⁻¹ at the water surface, abruptly decreasing at 4 m, and maintained a sustained load of 4 mg L⁻¹ until 30 m depth (Fig. 4D). Our results differ from those described by Silva *et al.* (2002) and Iriarte *et al.* (2014), for the Comau fjord and adjacent fjords, in which differences were found in oxygen concentrations with the range between 10 to 20 mg L⁻¹, and with fluorescence ranges between 5 and 75 ug L⁻¹, for the surface layer (0 – 10 m).

This system is highly stratified due to the interaction between Subantarctic Waters (SAAW), with high nutrient content at the bottom layer and the influence of different freshwater systems (high Si) present in the study area, resulting in a strong salinity gradient (Iriarte *et al.*, 2012).

Fig. 2. Aerial picture of the *H. akashiwo* bloom in the Comau Fjord in April 2021. Photo: Huinay Foundation.

Events with similar characteristics have been reported in the inland sea of Chiloé since the

beginning of the salmon farming. The first reported *H. akashiwo* bloom event occurred in 1988 in the Quintupeu fjord (at the vicinity of the Comau fjord) (Clément and Lembeye, 1993). A new event with high cell biomass was reported in 2000 and later in 2002 (Fuica *et al.*, 2007; Mardones *et al.*, 2012). These reports clearly identify *H. akashiwo* as a common species within the phytoplankton assemblage, even though massive outbreaks are quite sporadic.

An open question that remains is related to the mechanisms involved in the massive fish kills observed during the 2021 event. According to Barnes *et al.* (2011), 4 mg L⁻¹ is a critical oxygen threshold for the survival of *Salmo salar*. Based on our results, it is clear that low DO concentration (approx. 4 mg L⁻¹) measured below 5 m depth may have produced an important physiological stress on fish during the outbreak.

Under this scenario, cultured fish were trapped during days between the oxygenated surface layer containing potential ichthyotoxins produced by *H. akashiwo* and the low DO-bottom layer.

Fig. 3. *In situ* cells of *H. akashiwo* under a light microscope.

Fig. 4 A-D.: Vertical profiles of the water column in Comau fjord with CTD-O SeaBird 19.

Faced with the new global scenarios and extreme environmental conditions, the negative effects on high latitude systems (e.g., ENSO - Niño, global warming, acidification, etc.) are increasingly evident, which show a greater frequency and recurrence of HAB events. In the case of this study, *H. akashiwo* responds to the intrusion of freshwater from the ice fields of Patagonia, which generates a stratification system in the Comau fjord, which led to the proliferation of *H. akashiwo* in the surface layer, followed by a decrease in DO below 5 m, triggered physiological stress in large-scale cultured fish, generating high mortalities.

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